

APPRAISAL OF BANK'S LOAN DISBURSEMENT TO SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN NIGERIA AFTER BANK RECAPITALIZATION

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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, access to finance has been identified as a key element for SMEs to succeed in their drive to build productive capacity, to compete, to create jobs and to contribute to poverty alleviation in the country. Without finance, SMEs cannot acquire or absorb new technologies nor can they expand to compete in global markets or even strike business linkages with larger firms. Despite these, SMEs traditionally have faced difficulty in obtaining formal credit or equity from commercial banks. This study showed a downward trend despite recapitalisation by Nigeria commercial banks, it therefore conclude and recommend that there is more to Banks performance on stimulation of economy through SME than mere recapitalisation.

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, finance has been recognised as an essential tool for promoting small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). The Federal and State governments in Nigeria have recognized that for sustainable growth and development the financial empowerment of the SMEs is vital, being the repository of the predominantly poor in society. An important role of banks is to design ways of providing loans to informationally opaque small business (Berger, Klapper, and Udell 2001). However, a number of factors may affect the banking system's ability to provide credit to small borrowers in the future. There is evidence of bank consolidation across many countries of the world through mergers and acquisitions. These mega banks may be oriented towards transaction lending and providing capital markets services to large corporate clients and often less quantitative and qualitative relationship with small business. Re-capitalization of banks in Nigeria is intended among others to help mobilize domestic savings, deepening and broadening intermediation, Improve allocation of resources and helping to mobilize foreign savings.

Credit is the largest element of risk in the books of most banks and failures in the management of credit risk, by weakening individual banks and in some cases the banking whole, have contributed, to many episodes of financial instability. An increasing amount of research on credit risk is being carried out within financial firms, central banks, regulators and universities. However, in most developing countries like Nigeria, manufacturing SMEs are operating in an environment with weak institutions for technical and financial supports (Oyeyinka, 2002). They face severe legal and regulatory constraints and little institutional support is available for them for innovation. Hence, important technical affiliations, network capacity and ownership are crucial factors in the economic performance and innovative behaviour of these industries in such an environment.

Research Problems/Purpose: Despite recapitalisation of Nigeria banking industry and consequent declaration of large profit by the banks the real sector had not really felt their impact. This paper intends to analyze the accessibility of SMEs to bank loan and to ascertain whether recapitalisation offers an effective means of solving the problem of funding small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria, and determine the relationship between Bank recapitalisation, Bank loan disbursement to SME and their contribution to GDP.

The objectives are:-

- (i) To determine the effectiveness of banks in their role as economy stimulator; and
- (ii) Whether the recapitalisation improves loan disbursement to the economic engine rooms - the SME's.

Hypothesis:-

The study will investigate and hypothesis whether increased Bank capital base can influence adequate loan facilities to SME.

Literature Review

Small businesses do not conform to any neat parameters because much of their activities depend on the industry in which they operate also the personalities and aspirations of those in charge of these businesses. These factors vary from manufacturers to retailers; and high start-ups that are funded by venture capitalists to self-financed tradesmen and women for the purpose of making a living. (David.S and Nicholas, 2006). Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) occupy a place of pride in virtually every country or state. SMEs have aptly been referred to as "the engine of growth" and "catalysts for socio-economic transformation of any country." SMEs represent a veritable vehicle for the achievement of national economic objectives of employment generation and poverty reduction at low investment cost as well as the development of entrepreneurial capabilities including indigenous technology. SMEs in Nigeria can be Organized and Unorganized Enterprises. The organised enterprises have paid employees with a registered office while the unorganised enterprises are mainly made up of artisans who work in open spaces, or operate in temporary wooden workshop or structures, and mostly employ low rate or no salary paid workers. The major activity involved in this sector include; soap and detergents, fabrics, textile and leather, local blacksmith, tinsmith, ceramic, clothing and tailoring, timber and winning, bricks and cement, food processing, wood furniture, beverages, bakeries, electronic assembly, agro processing, chemical based products and mechanics (Sanni 2007).

Financial systems, the world over, play fundamental roles in development and growth of the economy. The effectiveness and efficiency in performing these roles, particularly the intermediation between the surplus and deficit unit of the economy, depends largely on the level of development of the financial system. It is to ensure its soundness that the financial sector appears to be the most regulated and controlled by the government and its agencies (Ogujiuba, Ohuche, Adenuga 2004). Stiglitz and Weis (1981) observe that small and medium scale firms with opportunities to invest in positive net present value projects may be blocked from doing so because of adverse selection. Adverse selection problems arise when potential providers of external finance (banks) cannot readily verify whether the firms have access to quality projects. Nonetheless, the liquidity ratio of the financiers plays a major role. Through the new minimum capital requirement, the number of banks in the country has been successfully reduced from eighty-nine to twenty-four. They are, therefore, better placed now to meet the funding needs of their clients in SMEs. In the past, the financial intermediation role of the banks became heavily impaired while the macroeconomic activities seriously slowed down. It was against this background, that the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) announced a major reform of the Nigerian banking industry. The recapitalization of the capital base of banks constituted the first phase of the reform policy in the banking sector of the Nigerian economy. Recapitalization in Nigeria comes with amendment to the existing banking laws. In July 2004, the new governor of the CBN announced the need for banks to increase their capital base to N25 billion all banks are expected to comply by December 2005 (Adegbaaju A. and Olokoyo F, 2008) with a view to provide verile banking system and support for economic growth and development.

In 2001, a study identified poor access to finance as the most critical constraint on small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. In fact, 50 percent of the surveyed enterprises received external finance while 79 percent indicated lack of financial resources as a major constraint (see Guardian. Nov, 26, 2001). The foregoing study confirms the risk-averse behaviour of banks in funding SMEs in Nigeria. Somoye & Ilo, (2009) also discussed the impact of lending on bank performance. They pointed out that the Nigerian government, through the CBN, set the lending rate for financial intermediaries at their various prevailing levels in the banking industry. To buttress their argument, they argued that the CBN set the rate to favour specific sectors in order to encourage or discourage lending to various sectors of the economy. However, the banks' desires to achieve favourable return on investment notwithstanding, the environmental factors play a vital role in banks' lending behaviour.

In recent year's banks in developed countries have launched a number of initiatives that both improve the profitability of lending to SMEs and also provide SMEs with better access to finance and to financial products that are better tailored to their needs (Aladekomo, 2003). A number of leading banks have demonstrated that providing financial services to SMEs can be turned into a highly profitable business. Although the business environments in developing countries and developed countries differ in many respects, the problems of servicing SME customers are similar, namely high-perceived risk, problems with information asymmetry and high administrative costs. Therefore, recent innovations in developed countries to improve SMEs access to credit can provide valuable insights for

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developing country banks to become more SME-oriented and to increase the volume and the quality of their services to this sector. Economic growth indices in Nigeria reflect the effective production capacities of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) not only on how they are funded, but the practical utilization of their operational philosophy and how this is integrated towards service delivery and uplifting society. As a result, several microlending institutions were established to enhance the development of SMES. Such micro credit institutions include the Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI), National Economic Reconstruction Fund (Nerfund), the Nigeria Agricultural and Rural Development Bank (NACRDB), the Microfinance Bank (MFB), and the Nigerian Export and Import Bank (NEXIM), and the liberalization of the banking sector. Howbeit, up till 2005 the number of banks operating in the country is about 89 with more than 50% having capital base of less than US\$10 million and about 3,300 branches. This compared to 8 banks in South Korea with about 4,500 branches or bank in South Africa with larger assets than all the 89 banks shows that the banking system is very marginal relative to its potentials and in comparism with other countries.(Ogujiuba, Ohuche, Adenuga 2004). Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), of whatever configuration, are an asset in the production chain of any economy, because of their impact on issues of job creation, provision of a wide variety of good services, income generation and efficient sources for micro – financing.

Despite their proactive nature, growth of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), have been lighted, because of inadequate access to finance, production schedules and marketing. This undoubtedly is a reflection of the changes in the monetary policies of our Nation. The comfort is that the governments (local, state and federal) are neither relenting nor giving up in their bid to revamp and invigorate the fortunes of SMEs as to enable them play the expected role in Nigeria's economic growth and development. This is evidenced by the government's recent establishment of as well as the mandate given to the Bank of Industry (BOI) and the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), the facilitation of the Bankers' Committee's institutionalisation of the Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS), the federal government's drive and focus on realizing the objective of NEPAD, the government's endorsement and support of multilateral agencies and loans, and the government's backing of international development finance facilities such as the European Investment Bank (EIB) facilities and the likes. Given the crucial role SMEs play in the industrial and economic growth and development of developing countries like Nigeria, the various governments in Nigeria cannot afford to relax in their efforts towards making the SME subsector very vibrant and productive(Onugu,2005).

SMEs Experience in Accessing Financial Resources

Due to the inability of SME's to raise their own finance and access financial services from formal sources (UNCTAD, 2001). This category of SMEs usually look to the banking sector and other financial intermediaries for instruments to finance working capital and to provide credit for short-term liquidity management. However, they often fail to access the financial resources in the required amounts because banks evaluate them on the basis of a checklist, as listed below:

- ✓ Audited finance statement for the last three years including management accounts;
- ✓ Project proposal highlighting strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats;
- ✓ Financial projectors;
- ✓ Monitoring costs;
- ✓ Credit or default risk because of the problem of information asymmetry;
- ✓ Enforcement costs.

Unfortunately, financial and accounting records are rarely in place, and where they are available, their accuracy is usually doubted. In instances where bank financing is provided, it is in most cases in amounts that are insufficient and at a high cost in relation to the term to maturity of loans they also apply simple and relatively backward technology in production and, therefore, the quality of their products are usually poor. There is a general lack of professionalism within this category of SMEs in terms of strategic planning procedures, decision-making processes and business planning, and management in general(Kasekende,200 I).

Banks Position in Financing SMEs

Consequently, commercial banks and investors have been reluctant to service SMEs because:- (1) SMEs are regarded by creditors and investors as high-risk borrowers due to insufficient assets and low

capitalization, vulnerability to market fluctuations and high mortality rates; (2) Information asymmetry arising from SMEs' lack of accounting records, inadequate financial statements or business plans makes it difficult for creditors and investors to assess the creditworthiness of potential SME proposals and (3) High administrative/transaction costs of lending or investing small amounts do not make SME financing a profitable business.

The absence of collateral or foolproof steps for its enforcement warrants special mention since it has been an important factor-inhibiting bank lending to SMEs particularly as banks do not just rely on their borrowers' past financial statements or projected earnings as the bases for their credit decisions. As a result, commercial banks are generally biased toward large corporate borrowers, who provide better business plans, have credit ratings, more reliable financial information, better chances of success and higher profitability for the banks. When banks do lend to SMEs, they tend to charge them a commission for assuming risk and apply tougher screening measures, which drives up costs on all sides.

Research Methodology

For the purpose of determining the relationship between Bank loan to the SMEs and its impact on the general economic development, secondary data was sourced from CBN statistical bulletin on: (i) Total Commercial Bank Loan, (ii) Loan to SMEs; and Gross Domestic Product (at current price). These are presented in Tables I & II i.e from 2000 to 2009 and the percentage composition in the pre-recapitalisation era was compared to post-recapitalisation era.

Ratio of Loans to SME's by Commercial Banks (₦)

Table 1: Pre-Recapitalization

Period	Commercial Banks Loans to SMEs	Total Commercial Banks Loans	Commercial Banks Loans to SMEs as %tage of Total Credit	GDP	%tage Growth of GDP
2000	44.54	508.30	8.76	4582	-
2001	52.43	796.16	6.59	4725	0.03
2002	82.37	954.63	8.63	6912	0.32
2003	90.18	1210.03	7.45	8487	0.19
2004	55.00	1519.24	3.62	11411	0.26

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin

Table II: Post-Recapitalization

Period	Commercial Banks Loans to SMEs	Total Commercial Banks Loans	Commercial Banks Loans to SMEs as %tage of Total Credit	GDP	%tage Growth of GDP
	Enterprises (N' Million)	(N' Million)	% of Total Credit		
2005	50,67	1,899.35	2.67	14572	0.22
2006	25,71	2,524.30	1.02	18566	0.22
2007	41,10	4,813.49	0.85	20657	0.10
2008	76.56	27,568.41	2.7	24296	0.15
2009	63.30	35167.20	0.72	24712	0.02

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

A study of the figures in Table 1 and 11 i.e. pre and post recapitalisation periods respectively showed that though the volume of total credit and loan disbursement to SMEs improved tremendously in the post recapitalisation era as expected but that is in absolute figure when relatively of loan to SME to total credit is factored in percentages, loan disbursement to SMEs in the pre recapitalisation era is better. Highest

proportion was 3.62% in pre-recapitalisation.

There was increase in GDP in the post-recapitalisation era, but given the proportion of loan disbursement to SMEs (i.e. lack of fund) how much of this increase in GDP could be attributable to the contribution of SMEs. (economic growth engine) Very small! Amazingly, the GDP itself is growing but the percentage growth is falling, more so after recapitalisation, which means money is not flowing to where it is needed for real economic growth.

The results above confirmed the risk-averse behaviour of banks in funding SMEs in Nigeria after the recapitalisation. The analysis of the access to credit market for small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria has established two important facts: (i) macroeconomic instability and uncertainty in the business environment has forced banks to lend short to SMEs; (ii) such overdrafts and short term loans are made available at high interest rates of over 26% and they are also relatively heavily collateralised. In a situation in which SMEs are mainly dependent on bank loans, this situation could be dangerous. The implication is that many SMEs do not have access to bank loans with grave implications for their growth and general economic development.

Despite efforts to encourage adequate fund flow to SMEs, the result has not being enthusiastic; the margin of loan to SMEs during post consolidation era is falling, i.e the economic engine house is grinding down. The growth in GDP could be concluded to be majorly a contribution of trading and services sectors and not manufacturing or real sector (SMEs) where the bank could have concentrated after such a good recapitalisation outing.

The Small and Medium Enterprises Equity Investment Scheme (SMEEIS)

The Small and Medium Enterprises Equity Investment Scheme facilitated by the CBN, was initiated by the Bankers' Committee (all the banks in Nigeria) as another means to funding small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. The scheme requires all banks to set aside 10 percent of their profit before tax annually for equity investment in small and medium enterprises. The scheme is to promote indigenous entrepreneurship, develop local technology, generate employment, facilitate the flow of funds from banks for the establishment of new, viable SMEs, ensure output expansion, re-distribute incomes and promote industrial linkages. The Scheme involves equity participation of banks in enterprises that they have appraised to be viable. The banks partner with the entrepreneurs for social and economic development.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Recapitalisation has in no way persuade banks to lend more to SMEs, if anything the bank are cost and risk implication conscious hence money seems to be flung elsewhere, perhaps where they can generate return quickly without minding the consequence on real sector growth it therefore behoves the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have to improve their management systems and adopt modern management techniques if they are to benefit from the opportunities offered by the formal sector. They need to improve their financial records and accounting systems. Proper records need to be kept and maintained and the books of accounts have to be clear and should reflect a realistic picture of their operations and financial conditions. A good system and books of accounts are not only helpful to the banks; they are also crucial in managing and monitoring business as well as guiding tax authorities.

Well-functioning and sustainable mechanisms for SME financing require institution building and a market approach. Lending institutions must improve their ability to provide financial services to SMEs through commercial mechanisms that lower costs and minimize their risk exposure. Only in this way will financial institutions find SME lending to be more profitable, and thus be encouraged to construct lending programmes targeted at SMEs.

Part of the reluctance of banks to lend to SMEs is the banks' inability to properly evaluate the position of SMEs because of the lack of reliable financial information. Banks and regulatory authorities at times demand more information than what is publicly made available or required. In addition financial analysts, rating agencies or business intelligence providers can generate additional information, which is available to creditors and investors, at additional cost.

REFERENCES

- Aladekomo, F. O. 2003: "The Small and Medium Enterprises' (SME) Landscape: Environment, Government policies, Programmes, and Institutional support." A paper delivered at the two-day workshop on "Strategies for Operationalising Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS) in Nigeria" on 23 - 24 August, 2003, at WEMA Bank Training School, Oba Akran Avenue, Ikeja, Lagos, Nigeria.
- Adegbaju A. and Olokoyo F.(2008) Recapitalization and Banks' Performance: A Case Study of Nigerian Banks African Economic and Business Review Vol. 6 NO.1, Spring 2008. ISSN 1109-5609.
- Berger and Klapper F. L., Udell, G. F. (2001). The ability of banks to lend to informationally Opaque Small Business, Federal Reserve Bank working paper, Washington D.C.
- CBN. (2004): "Progress Report on SMIEIS" Accessible from <http://www.cenbank.org>.
- David. S. and Nicholas. (2006): Small Business Management & Entrepreneurship 5th Edition.
- Feldman, R., (1997): Banks and a Big Change in Technology Called Credit Scoring. The Region Federal Reserve Bank of Minneapolis, September 19-25, Guardian Newspaper, Nov, 26, 2001.
- Kasekende,L.(2001): Improving The Competitiveness Of SMEs In Developing Countries., UNITED NATIONS New York and Geneva,
- Mester L.J (1998): On the Profitability and Cost of Relationship Lending Journal of Banking and Finance 22, 873-897
- Ogujiuba, Ohuche, Adenuga (2004): Credit Availability to Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Nigeria: Importance of New Capital Base for Banks - Background and Issues. Working Paper Series.
- Odedokun, M O (1998): Effectiveness of Selective Credit Policies Alternative Framework of Evaluation World Development Vol. 16, pp. 120 - 122.
- Oyeyinka B.-Oyelaran, (2002): Manufacturing response in a national system of innovation: evidence from the brewing firms in Nigeria. Discussion Paper Series of The United Nations University, Institute of New Technologies (INTECH). Accessed on May 2005 from <http://www.intech.unu.edu>.
- Onugu.B.A(2005): Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects. A Dissertation Submitted To The St. Clements University In Partial Fulfillment Of The Requirements For The Award Of The Degree of Doctor of Philosophy In Management.
- Stiglitz, J. and A. Weiss, (1981): Credit Rationing in Markets with Imperfect Information, American Economic Review 71, 93-40.
- Somoye & Ilo (2009): The impact of Macroeconomic Instability on Banking sector lending behavior in Nigeria. Journal of Money, Investment and banking, Issue 7 (online), available at www.eurojournal.com.
- Sanni, O.(2007): Small Scale Industry: Problems Of Establishing Small Business Enterprise In Nigeria Case Study: Alahtee Nigeria Limited. An Unpublished dissertation submitted to the Department of Business Economics and Tourisms, Vassa Polytechnics,
- UNCTAD 2001: Survey of Good Practice in Public-Private Sector Dialogue. Enterprise Development Series, New York and Geneva: United Nations.